

MACHADO, Ana Maria. **Caro professor**. São Paulo: Global, 2017.

REVIEW¹

Maria das Graças Monteiro Castro²

Ana Maria Machado is an icon of literature for children and young people. Hors-Concours in the Fnlij Prize, she won Hans Christian Andersen/ibby and the National Literary Prize Machado de Assis for her entire work. As author of children's books, she was the first to enter the Brazilian Academy of Letters. *Caro professor* (Dear Teacher) is a work that brings together texts aimed at educators, and discusses topics such as spelling reforms, teacher's role, quality of education and citizenship building. It is a text full of her personal memories as a student, teacher, journalist and author.

Keywords: Education. Teaching-learning. Linguistics.

¹ Synopsis of the book for the Catalog Of The Children's Book Fair 2018 Bologna. Books published in 2017 and reviewed in 2018. Review and English version: Gisele Dionísio da Silva

² Voter.